

CLASSIFICATION OF SPEECH DISORDERS

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Abstract: This article is scientifically based on the forms and types of speech disorders imagination, effective ways to eliminate these disorders, 11 types of speech disorders in speech therapy form and 9 of them are the result of oral speech and disorders of production in various processes information is provided.

Keywords: Logopedia, dysphonia (aphonia), tachylalia, bradylalia, stuttering, dyslalia, rhinolalia, dysarthria (anarthria), alalia, aphasia, written dyslexia (alexia), dysgraphia (agraphia).

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Speech therapy is a means of special education and training about speech disorders is a pedagogical science of studying, correcting and preventing disorders. Speech therapy speech studies the causes, mechanisms, symptoms, and flow structure of dysfunction. Therefore, it is added to the special pedagogy. These are scientifically based ideas about the forms and types of speech disorders a prerequisite for the development of effective methods of eliminating violations is considered There are many researchers in all historical periods of the development of the science of speech therapy tried to classify speech disorders with types. But in the present era and the problem of classification is not only speech disorders, but also speech disorders remains one of the important problems of other scientific disciplines. The following can be included in such disciplines: neurophysiology, medicine, pathopsychology and branches of neuropsychology, special psychology and pedagogy: oligophrenopedagogy, deaf pedagogy, typhlopedagogy.[1]

The difficulty of classifying speech disorders is due to some reasons, among them, the mechanism of speech itself is not sufficiently studied, as well as The main reason is the inconsistency of researchers' points of view on the issue of principles takes place, and the classification should be built on the basis of the above principles. The science of speech therapy does not have its own classification in its initial stages of formation and he did not even raise the question of the need to develop it. After all, it is Europe of the achievements of medicine in the study of speech disorders classifications collected at the end of the 19th and the beginning of the 20th centuries relied on. A. Kussmaul's classification is one of the first classifications (1877), it is speech criticized the preconceived notions about the types of disorders; them systematized, arranged the terms. He later calls it clinical

started) foreign and Russian researchers of the first quarter of the 20th century: V. Oltushevsky, G. Gutsman, E. Freshels, S. M. Dobrogayev and other works was taken as a basis. Speech disorders in adults and children are some of the mental functions in childhood "improper formation" of its components or a pathogen in the human nervous system at a mature age to be the result of a malfunction of the already formed speech system due to its influence possible Depending on the time of appearance of dysfunction, its nature and intensity, speech changes depending on the symptoms and course of the disorder. Below are two of the speech disorders used in health care and education the most common classification is given:

1. Psychological-pedagogical classification Communication disorders:

-Phonetic-phonemic underdevelopment of speech (FFNR);

- fully developed speech (NTR), alalia, aphasia Violation of the rules for the use of communication tools;

- Stuttering.

2. Medical-pedagogical classification with traditional medicine for speech therapy relies on cooperation, but in contrast to medical classification, in which speech is separated types of disorders are not related to disease forms. Speech impairment

-Dysphonia (aphonia) - due to pathological changes of the sound apparatus absence or weakening of phonation. Synonyms: sound distortion, phonation disorders, phonotoral disorders, vocal disorders;

-Bradylalia is a pathological slow pace of speech. Meaning: bradyphrasy. Manifested in the slow production of the speech program, centrally linked and can be organic or functional in nature. Tachylalia is a pathologically accelerated rate of speech. Meaning: tachyphrasy. Articles are manifested in the accelerated implementation of the speech program, centrally by nature, it is centrally connected, organic or functional. Stuttering is a voluntary part of the muscles of the speech apparatus it is a violation of tempo and tone as a result of gravity. Meaning: logoneurosis. Centrally connected, functional or organic look has, appears more in the development of the child's speech;

-Dyslalia - pronunciation of sounds with preservation of intelligence and hearing ability violation ;

-Rhinolalia (nasal speech) - anatomical in the peripheral part of the speech analyser voice pronunciation and voice timbre disorders due to the defect;

-Dysarthria - insufficient level of muscles that provide the function of speech vocal pronunciation and prosodic speech as a result of innervation disorders (intonation, tone, rhythm, pitch) side disorder. Dysarthria - speech apparatus is a speech disorder caused by pronunciation due to an organic disorder of innervation.

The term dysarthria is derived from the Greek words dis - piece and arthon - attachment. means. Dysarthria is a central organic nerve disorder is considered;

-Alalia - speech of a child in the womb or in the early stages of development organic injury of the speech sphere of the cerebral cortex before its formation due to non-continuous development. The term "Alalia" (Greek a - no, Latin lalio - speech) translation refers to the absence of speech, the state of non-speech - speech disorders observed in literature since ancient times. "Alalia" in special literature In addition to the term, they used the following terms to denote this speech defect: "Congenital aphasia", "Ontogenetic aphasia", "Developmental aphasia", "Dysphasia", "Speech retardation of development", "Constitutional retardation of speech", "Language acquisition flaws" etc.[2]

Aphasia - in connection with damage to a specific part of the brain complete or partial loss of speech. Synonyms: speech disorder, loss. Child speech as a result of brain injury, neuroinfection or brain tumor if the loss occurs after the formation of speech, then it is called infantile aphasia is called If the disorder occurred at an older age, then the idea of aphasia is conducted. Impairment of written speech. It is divided into two groups depending on which type it is broken is separated. Impairment of writing when productive type is impaired, prescription writing activity when it is broken - the weakening of the reading is reversed.

1. Dyslexia is a partially specific disorder of the reading process.

2. Dysgraphia is a partially specific disorder of the writing process.

When the optical-spatial image of the letter is not stable, the letters are mixed up orIt is manifested in falling, describing the word-syllable composition and sentence construction will be An opinion about agraphia when the writing process is not formed during teaching is conducted. Thus, 11 forms of speech disorders are distinguished in speech therapy, 9 of them constitutes the result of oral speech and disorders in various processes of production. The remaining 2 forms are distinguished in connection with the process of distortion of written speech including distortions. Speech disorders include dysphonia (aphonia), tachylalia, bradylalia, stuttering, dyslalia, rhinolalia, dysarthria (anarthria), alalia, aphasia is distinguished; Dyslexia (alexia) and dysgraphia are among the disorders of written speech (graphia) is separated. The above classifications include only such forms of speech disorders. It is included that they are shown in the speech therapy literature and the methods applied to them are developed developed. Within each form of speech disorders, types and subtypes are distinguished, which are reflected in the next chapters. In this regard, it should be mentioned that the line In some cases, it is not a variant of speech disorders related to one form, but a separate disorder shows. For example, to dyslalia, on the one hand, articulatory-phonetic disorders, i.e defects in the production of private sounds related to the level of the

speech norm of speech, on the other hand, sounds related to unformed operations phonetic, which makes a choice and refers to the level of (linguistic) variation of the statement distortions are included. The inconsistency of the above classification is speech (psychological and physiological) mechanisms in connection with the growth of knowledge and new researches in speech therapy it became especially noticeable during the modern development of science. Each in the development of science new knowledge requires changes to previous ideas. that is why The issue of speech disorders is relevant for further production of speech therapy remains the task.[3]

Psychological-pedagogical classification, the point of application of medical classifications in the pedagogical process was created as a result of critical analysis from the point of view (this method is logopedic influence is called). Such an analysis of speech therapy for teaching children with impaired speech development and has become very important in relation to involvement in education. The classification described above reflects the current state of speech therapy theory makes There are no contradictions between them, they complement each other. In this textbook both options are used as the basis of its structure. The task of speech therapy is to improve the regulation of speech disorders. The above classifications lead more children to primary underdevelopment of speech, i.e performance in relation to speech disorders in normal hearing and mental aspect developed.[4]

By the way, children in this category are not the same in their composition: they are not mentally retarded to the degree, vision and locomotor apparatus including spoiled children. Showing above the classification developed in speech therapy Can it be applied to children with speech disorders of the previous category or new it is important to decide whether research is necessary. Also, regulate the speech disorders of mentally retarded and hearing impaired children The question of putting is also a very important and complicated issue.

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